

THE COHERENCE OF MEANS INDICATING II PERSON MEANING IN THE UZBEK LANGUAGE

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Abstract. The article analyzes the synonymy of second person means in the Uzbek literary language and the use of such means in speech (sentence, text). The expression of the meaning of the first person in speech is described by one, two, three means. In this regard, attention is drawn to the economical use of personal pronouns. Also analyzed are the use of second person forms in the meaning of other persons, the generalization of the meaning of means expressing the first person, the expression of the meaning of a person using the context of forms that do not express faces. Component analysis shows that the three meanings (person, number and respect) of conjugation affixes and personal pronouns are the same.

Key words: meaning of a person, synonymy of words and affixes, denotative property of synonymous means, connotative property of synonymous means, personal pronoun, subject, theme, rheme, change in the paradigmatic property of means of the second person. In the traditional Uzbek linguistic studies of the 20th century, the peculiarity of language phenomena in the Uzbek language was predominantly not characterized by its own distinctive structure, but rather was equated and designated by Russian vocabulary and analogies. Consequently, the equivalence of word with word and additional with additional in Russian linguistics was understood, while the equivalence of word with additional was left unaddressed [2: 231]. G. Zikrillayev in the Independence and mother tongue structure education program explains the equivalence of word and additional meanings as follows: Since most additives stem from the main word, there is equivalence among them. Therefore, the meaning that can be expressed by some words can also be expressed by additional forms. Person, number, and respect represent this, they are expressed with -m, -man, -(a)y and men; -ng, -san and sen; -k, -miz, -(a)ylik and biz; -siz, -(i)ngiz and siz. If emphasis is not indicated in speech, pronoun cannot be used in the sentence, only additional words are used: Keldim. Olding. Borasiz. There is no direct word in this way. It also indicates the meaning of emphasis. Therefore, it is not correct to say subject omits [1: 59 – 60]. The correlation of words and suffixes

seen in the aforementioned ones is related to the main feature of the structure of the Uzbek literary language formation (cognitive economy) and if a specific meaning is expressed with additional meaning, if the emphasis is not highlighted, the corresponding word is used. This article analyzes the semantic compatibility of the means of the second person, their use in speech (speech, text) to clarify and strengthen each other's meaning.

The main part. In the Uzbek literary language, the meaning of the second person is expressed by the following means: 1) the root, base of the verb, 2) auxiliary clause (-san, -ng, -siz, -ngiz, -sanlar, -sizlar, -nglar, -nizlar, -(i)nglar, -(i)ngizlar, -laring), 3) personal pronouns (sen, siz, senlar, sizlar) 4) reflexive pronoun (o'zing, o'zingiz, o'zlaring, o'zlaringiz) action noun, participle, 5) collective, disjunctive and interrogative pronouns which were taken possessive clauses 6) root of noun (in function of exclamatory), 7) action noun, participle (borishing, borganing).

The linguistic analysis of the verb's stem, root, and modifying affixes indicates that the second person singular and plural pronouns share three grammatical meanings (person, number, and respect), showing their similarity. This allows us considering them as synonymous in terms of meaning (systemic, paradigmatic synonyms). Analyzing the differences between synonymous means enables contextual and textual analysis, similar to the analysis of first person pronouns. Contextual and textual analysis demonstrates their lack of stylistic (connotative) specificity.

From synonymic means, the verb's stem, and the additions which gives the meanings of person, number, and respect also indicate the subject performing the action. It's not primarily evident in the utterance. The personal (and possessive - F.S.) pronoun is used to emphasize the subject having served its purpose [2: 237].

The personal pronoun (and self - F.S.) is used sparingly as it serves to emphasize the subject (owner) [2: 237]. The use or non-use of the personal and personal pronouns is related to the emotional and non-emotional nature of the statement, more precisely, the valence of the adverbial means (the means of forming the clause) and the actual (communicative, speech) division of the sentence. If the verbal objective is to convey a message (thought, question, command, request) in an efficient manner, it is expressed in Uzbek as a single-word sentence. This word primarily serves the function of the predicate. Thus, in such a sentence, both components of the actual division (theme and rheme) are present within the same medium. In this way, the division of the theme and

rheme in an actual sentence will be present in the same unit. When specifying the speech act theme, a micro or macro context is used as a linguistic tool (olmosh).

If it is not necessary to emphasize the addressee (clarifying the theme or indicating the rheme), the meaning of the second person will be expressed with an additional component that is a suffix indicating the stem of the verb. In this case, the smallest unit of speech consists of a single word (segment). The form of this type of sentence is based on the stem of an independent verb. From the point of contextual analysis, such a sentence is considered to have minimal context in terms of volume and neutral context in terms of specificity. In the following examples, the meaning of the addressee is expressed through the stem of an independent verb: Tur! (S. Ahmad, Ufq, 9) [- What should I do now?] Qoch. (T. Murod, Otamdan qolgan dalalar).

In both examples personal pronoun, you was not utilized. In the root system of verb number (singular), imperatives, future simple, declarative, neutral, active voice, neutral stance meanings are meant yet omitted. Moreover, when it conveys message in the form of sentence words mastery and conciseness can be shown in great level.

When the sentence is made of one word meaning of addressee can be shown by auxiliary clauses: – Ikrommisan?(S. Ahmad, Ufq, 7). In this sentence noun and particle (Ikrommi) means rheme, -san, auxiliary clause means topic. In this sentence you, personal pronoun is not used. In these examples, sen, senlar, siz , sizlar, personal pronouns are not utilized: –Ketmaysanmi? (S. Ahmad, Ufq, 164) – Keldilaringmi? (S. Ahmad, Ufq, 127) – Tanimayapsizmi? (T. Murod, Otamdan qolgan dalalar) – Qo'rqmanglar. (Sh. Xolmirzayev, Ot yili, 447).

In the above examples, only the subject is explicitly stated, but in the following examples, the object (in addition to the subject) is also stated: [- O'zbekcha gapiravering.] Bilasiz-ku. (S. Ahmad, Ufq, 88) [- Trassada edim. Esh polvonni iniga tiqib kelyapman.] – Urdingmi? (S. Ahmad, Ufq, 188). In the first example, the object was not utilized, which is omitted in the preceding sentence and became case. In the second example, the object is present in the preceding sentence. Therefore, this part is not utilized in these sentences.

If it is not necessary to emphasize the subject in microdialogs, the meaning of the II person can be expressed using reflexive pronouns: – Yana o'zing bilasan, o'g'lim. Jigarchilik, bir kun kelib afsus qilib yurmasang bo'lgani. Yoshsan, bolasan, bilmaysan. Otaga farzand dog'i qanaqa bo'lishini bilmaysan.

Bu gaplarni ota bo'lganingda bilasan. (S. Ahmad, Ufq, 41). In this microdialogue, personal pronouns (sen) were used in sentences where reflexive pronouns were mentioned only in the first sentence.

When emphasizing the purpose of speech act, the pronouns (sen, siz, senlar, sizlar, o'zing, o'zingiz, o'zlaring) are used in the text to clarify the context for the second person. In this way, the speech act at least includes a word: – Sen boraver. (S. Ahmad, Ufq, 35) – Siz bormaysiz. (S. Ahmad, Ufq, 535) In both examples where emphasizing the listener is intended, pronouns (sen, siz) are used. These pronouns emphasize the additional meaning that performs the role of the theme.

When speaker compared with the listener, even if placed in opposition, the emphasis is on the pronoun used : – Yo'q, oyim ruxsat bermaydilar, **men** yoshman, **siz** qarisiz... (M. M. Do'st, Galatepaga qaytish) – **Sen** bormasang, **o'zim** ketaman. (S. Ahmad, Ufq, 536) In the first example, the speaker compares himself with the listener from a youth perspective. In the second example, the speaker opposes himself to the listener. Therefore, in the first sentence, the pronouns "men" and "siz" are used, while in the second example, **sen** and **o'zim** pronouns are used. The listener can also be compared to others: – **Odamlar** ishini qilib tushlikka chiqdi. **Sen** hali ham bolishdan boshingni uzmapsan. Ahmoq! (S. Ahmad, Ufq, 9) In this example, the emphasis is on the subject in the first sentence with a noun, and by a pronoun in the second sentence.

Emphasizing the listener can also be done by using a pronoun and changing its position: Tuproqni **senlar** qazimaysanlar, Jo'ravoy aka ikki yigit beradi. (S. Ahmad, Ufq, 121). Since the goal is to emphasize the listener, the pronoun you(senlar) is used and brought to the front of the participle. In this case, the pronoun is part of the rhema.

A rhyming pronoun can also be used several times in the microtext to increase emphasis: Butun umrini, jonini, rohatini bag'ishlagan onaga shumi mukofot? Alifdek qomatini **sen** bukding, yuzlariga ajinlarni **sen** solding, ko'zlaridagi nurni **sen** o'g'irlading, shu yorug' dunyoni qorong'i zindon qilding. (S. Ahmad, Ufq, 466). In this example, the speaker is the father (Ikromjon), and the listener is his son (Tursunboy), who fled the war and was hiding in the moor. Despite his illness, his mother brings him food every day so that Tursunboy does not go hungry. In the end, she dies because of the mental pain and illness caused by thinking about her child. Tursunboy, watching his mother being taken to the funeral, does not come out of the grove and looks

indifferently. I know when Ikramjon told his son that your mother is dead. He says that I was watching when they were taking you to the burial. Then the father lost himself and said the above words to his son with pain and hatred. The repeated use of a pronoun in front of a participle emphasizes the listener and serves to show the speaker's emotion (negative attitude). Therefore, the pronoun served to express the connotation.

In an elucidating context, various means of listeners can be utilized to specify. In the specified example, the interlocutor is identified through the common noun – O'g'lim, turdingmi. (S. Ahmad, Ufq, 12) In reality, the root of the noun designates the third person. In this sentence, with the awkward tool (the form of the verb's second person) the interlocutor is being meant. The part of the concrete tool is designated also by proper noun. Proper noun means the call of the single person and this conveys exactly the person who is the listener: **Jannat**, Ikromga o'zing xabar qil. (S. Ahmad, Ufq, 13) In one sentence, both the common and proper noun are utilized. In this case, with the auxiliary clause the exact interlocutor is defined: **Tursunboy, bolaginam**, qanisan? (S. Ahmad, Ufq, 9). A personal pronoun is used together with a related noun in a sentence. In this case, the relative noun serves to clarify the listener, and the personal pronoun serves to emphasize it: **Otaxon, siz** Aziz polvonning dadasimisiz? (S. Ahmad, Ufq, 112) The word (dadasi) which is a participle is also clarifying the listener.

Summary. In the Uzbek literary language, the meaning of the second person is expressed by the following means: 1) the root of the verb, 2) auxiliary clauses (-san, -ng, -siz, -ngiz, -sanlar, -sizlar, -nglar, -ngizlar, -(i)nglar, -(i)ngizlar, -laring), 3) personal pronoun (sen siz senlar sizlar), 4) reflexive pronoun (o'zing o'zingiz o'zlaring o'zlarinigiz), 5) possessive pronoun with endings, interrogative (hammangiz, har biringiz, qaysingiz, nechtangiz), 6) root of noun (in function of exclamatory), 7) action noun (borishing, borganing) The linguistic analysis of the verb's stem, root, and modifying affixes indicates that the second person singular and plural pronouns share three grammatical meanings (person, number, and respect), showing their similarity. This allows us considering them as synonymous in terms of meaning (systemic, paradigmatic synonyms). Analyzing the differences between synonymous means enables contextual and textual analysis, similar to the analysis of first person pronouns. Contextual and textual analysis demonstrates their lack of stylistic (connotative) specificity. This is a text explaining how related (system, paradigmatic synonym) words can be viewed as synonymous. Identifying the difference between related words

helps in contextual and textual analysis, like analyzing personal pronouns to understand the contextual and textual differences. Contextual and textual analysis indicates their stylistic (connotative) properties that are inappropriate. Synonymous words shape the subject performing the action, such as verb routes, persons, numbers, and respect markers. They also specify the subject (subject) playing an important role in the sentence. The use of personal pronouns mainly emphasizes the subject to underline their individuality. In order to emphasize the task recipient, the speech purpose dictates the use of personal pronouns (you, your, yours, yourself) in the text. Such text serves as a guiding context for the clarification of the second-person means.

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